

Practitioners' perception of home office in agile teams during the Covid-19 pandemic

The survey will take approximately 10 minutes to complete. This questionnaire aims to identify, in the perception of Software Engineering employees, aspects of home office work in agile teams during the Covid-19 pandemic, identify tools and methods adopted to work. We greatly appreciate the participation of people who have worked with agile teams during this period.

Declaration of consent

By responding to this survey, you consent to the researcher obtaining, using and disclosing the anonymous information provided as described below.

Conditions

1. I understand that all information is confidential. I will not be identified personally. I agree to complete the survey for research purposes and that data derived from this anonymous survey may be published in journals, conferences and blog posts.
2. I understand that my participation in this research is completely voluntary and that refusal to participate will not incur any penalty or loss of benefits. If I want, I can cancel my participation at any time. I also understand that if I choose to participate, I may decline to answer any questions that I do not feel comfortable answering.
3. I understand that I can contact the researcher if I have any questions about the research. I understand that my consent will not directly benefit me. I am also aware that the author will keep the collected data in perpetuity and may use the data for future academic work.
4. By clicking the button below, I freely agree and acknowledge my rights as a voluntary research participant as described above and give consent to the researcher to use my information in carrying out research in the areas mentioned above.

* mandatory

1. Please tell us your Country, State and City where that you work. *

2. How old are you? *

less than 21 years

21 to 25 years

26 to 30 years

31 to 35 years

36 to 40 years

41 to 45 years

46 to 50 years

51 to 55 years old
56 to 60 years
over 60 years

3. What is your education level? *

Graduation student
Graduation
Specialization
Master's degree
Doctorate degree
Post doctoral

4. How long have you been working in the ITC (Information Technology and Communication) field? *

less than 1 year
from 1 to 3 years old
From 4 to 6 years
from 7 to 10 years
from 11 to 15 years old
from 16 to 20 years old
more than 20 years

5. What is the area of activity of the organization in which you participate/participated in a software development project? *

Federal Public Administration
State Public Administration
State company (Serpro, BB, CEF, Correios, etc.)
Private software development company
Collaboration/research projects
Open-source projects

6. What was the main role (functions) that you play/have played in a software development project? *

Requirements analyst
Software engineer
Specialist in human computer interaction
Project manager
Data modeling
Software programmer/developer
Designer / Designer
Software tester
I have never participated in a software development project

Pandemic related issues

7. When did your institution suspend face-to-face personal activities due to Covid-19? Please reply using DD/MM/YYYY. If not suspended, reply "Not suspended". *

8. Check the alternatives that define your professional life after the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic. *

My workplace was closed, and I could not carry out activities remotely.

My workplace was closed, but activities continued fully, in remote mode.

My workplace was closed, but activities continued partially, in remote mode.

My workplace was not closed, but activities continued partially, in remote mode.

My workplace was not closed, and activities continued face-to-face.

My workplace was partially closed, and activities continued XXXXX

9. In your opinion, has this period of closure of organizations that imposed an adaptation to remote work affected your productivity? *

No

Yes - negatively

Yes - positively

10. Why?

Questions related to agile teams

11. What agile method / framework do you use? *

Kanban

Scrumban

XP

scrum

Other

12. What is your current role on the team? *

Coach

Developer

Scrum Master
Product Owner
Other

13. Has the interaction between IT and the business area improved with the adoption of remote work? *

I totally disagree
I disagree
Neutral
I agree
I totally agree

14. Why?

15. What tools and methods were adopted?

16. Has transparency (understanding what needs to be done, what is being done, etc.) improved with the adoption of remote work? *

I totally disagree
I disagree
Neutral
I agree
I totally agree

17. Why?

18. What tools and methods were adopted?

19. Has collaboration between development team members improved with the adoption of remote work? *

I totally disagree
I disagree
Neutral
I agree
I totally agree

20. Why?

21. What tools and methods were adopted?

22. Has team communication become more effective with the adoption of remote work? *

I totally disagree
I disagree
Neutral
I agree
I totally agree

23. Why?

24. What tools and methods were adopted?

25. Has your agile team become more productive with the adoption of remote work? *

I totally disagree
I disagree
Neutral
I agree
I totally agree

26. Why?

27. What tools and methods were adopted?

28. Were impediments or problems resolved more quickly with the adoption of remote work? *

I totally disagree
I disagree
Neutral
I agree
I totally agree

29. Why?

30. What tools and methods were adopted?

31. Could you describe whether, in your perception, working with agile teams remotely was more challenging than in person. Did you encounter the same difficulties and challenges? Or did others appear? Which are?

32. What were the solutions and proposals to mitigate or improve this remote work process?

33. Could you describe other considerations that you think are important that were not addressed in the questionnaire.